

Body-Weight Cycling and Risk of Diabetic Kidney Disease in People with Type 1 Diabetes in the DCCT/EDIC Population

Supplemental Material

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Supplemental Table 1. Characteristics of participants at DCCT baseline by 40% eGFR decline and A3 albuminuria outcomes during follow-up

	40% Decline in eGFR			Incident A3 albuminuria		
	No	Yes	p	No	Yes	p
N	1163	269		1264	168	
DCCT group: intensive treatment, n (%)	589 (51)	117 (43)	0.03	659 (52)	47 (28)	<0.0001
Sex: male, n (%)	639 (55)	118 (44)	0.001	641 (51)	116 (69)	<0.0001
Age, years	27 ± 7	27 ± 8	0.88	27 ± 7	26 ± 8	0.03
BMI, kg/m ²	23.4 ± 2.8	23.6 ± 2.8	0.38	23.4 ± 2.8	24.0 ± 2.9	0.008
Duration of diabetes, years	5.8 ± 4.2	6.0 ± 4.0	0.65	5.8 ± 4.2	6.2 ± 3.9	0.25
HbA1c, %	8.7 ± 1.5	9.5 ± 1.7	<0.0001	8.7 ± 1.5	10.0 ± 1.8	<0.0001
HbA1c, mmol/mol	72 ± 17	80 ± 19	<0.0001	72 ± 16	86 ± 19	<0.0001
Systolic BP, mmHg	115 ± 11	114 ± 12	0.89	114 ± 11	116 ± 12	0.03
Diastolic BP, mmHg	73 ± 8	73 ± 9	0.38	73 ± 8	74 ± 9	0.06
Mean BP, mmHg	87 ± 8	87 ± 9	0.60	87 ± 8	88 ± 8	0.03
Arterial hypertension, n (%)	2 (0.17)	0 (0)	0.99	2 (0.2)	0 (0)	0.99
Total cholesterol, mmol/L	4.54 ± 0.85	4.68 ± 0.88	0.01	4.55 ± 0.86	4.67 ± 0.83	0.10
LDL-cholesterol, mmol/L	2.82 ± 0.75	2.92 ± 0.74	0.05	2.83 ± 0.76	2.93 ± 0.70	0.10
HDL-cholesterol, mmol/L	1.31 ± 0.31	1.30 ± 0.34	0.80	1.32 ± 0.32	1.24 ± 0.34	0.004
Triglycerides, mmol/L*	0.78 [0.42]	0.87 [0.50]	<0.0001	0.79 [0.42]	0.97 [0.63]	<0.0001
Hyperlipidemia, n (%)	255 (22)	73 (27)	0.06	285 (23)	43 (26)	0.38

eGFR, ml/min/1.73m ²	125 ± 14	129 ± 16	0.0004	125 ± 14	131 ± 15	<0.0001
AER, mg/24h*	10 [10]	13 [14]	0.05	10 [11]	16 [18]	<0.0001
AER > 30 mg/24h, n (%)	117 (10)	40 (15)	0.03	120 (9)	37 (22)	<0.0001
Tobacco smoking, n (%)	242 (21)	60 (22)	0.62	253 (20)	49 (29)	0.007

Continuous data expressed as mean ± SD or as median [IQR]*. Categorical data expressed as number (%). Statistics are Student's t test, *Wilcoxon test or Fisher's exact test. Arterial hypertension: Systolic BP >140 mmHg or Diastolic BP >90 mmHg or use of antihypertensive drug. Hyperlipidemia: LDL-cholesterol $3.37 \geq$ mmol/L (130 mg/dl) or use of lipid-lowering drug. eGFR: estimated glomerular filtration rate. AER: Urinary albumin excretion rate.

Supplemental Table 2. Unadjusted risk of outcomes during the DCCT+EDIC follow-up by indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight during the DCCT

	HR or OR* (95% C.I.)	p
40% eGFR decline		
VIM	1.20 (1.08 – 1.34)	0.0009
ASV	1.18 (1.06 – 1.32)	0.004
SD_bw	1.16 (1.04 – 1.28)	0.001
REL_ASV	1.20 (1.07 – 1.33)	0.002
Doubling of SCR		
VIM	1.46 (1.26 – 1.66)	<0.0001
ASV	1.30 (1.12 – 1.50)	0.001
SD_bw	1.34 (1.16 – 1.54)	0.0002
REL_ASV	1.36 (1.18 – 1.55)	<0.0001
CKD Stage 3		
VIM	1.17 (1.00 – 1.36)	0.05
ASV	1.26 (1.08 – 1.45)	0.004
SD_bw	1.16 (0.99 – 1.35)	0.06
REL_ASV	1.21 (1.03 – 1.39)	0.02
Rapid decline in eGFR*		
VIM	1.36 (1.14 – 1.60)	0.0008
ASV	1.31 (1.10 – 1.55)	0.003
SD_bw	1.29 (1.08 – 1.53)	0.006
REL_ASV	1.31 (1.10 – 1.55)	0.003
A2 albuminuria		
VIM	1.09 (0.99 – 1.20)	0.09
ASV	1.11 (1.01 – 1.22)	0.04
SD_bw	1.08 (0.98 – 1.19)	0.11
REL_ASV	1.10 (0.99 – 1.20)	0.07
A3 albuminuria		
VIM	1.08 (0.93 – 1.25)	0.26
ASV	1.14 (0.99 – 1.30)	0.06
SD_bw	1.08 (0.93 – 1.24)	0.28
REL_ASV	1.10 (0.95 – 1.26)	0.19

Hazard Ratios (HR; Cox proportional hazards survival regression analyses) for the incidence of outcomes and *Odds Ratios (OR; logistic regression analyses) for the occurrence of Rapid decline in eGFR during follow-up computed for 1 SD of the body-weight variability indices expressed as Z-scores. See methods for definitions of the indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight and outcomes.

Supplemental Table 3. Indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight during the DCCT follow-up and risk of use of ACE inhibitors or ARB during EDIC follow-up.

	Model 1		Model 2	
	HR (95% C.I.)	p	HR (95% C.I.)	p
VIM	1.20 (1.12 – 1.29)	<0.0001	1.16 (1.07 – 1.26)	0.0006
ASV	1.10 (1.02 – 1.18)	0.01	1.04 (0.96 – 1.12)	0.30
SD_bw	1.17 (1.10 – 1.26)	<0.0001	1.13 (1.04 – 1.23)	0.006
REL_ASV	1.12 (1.04 – 1.20)	0.004	1.06 (0.99 – 1.15)	0.09

Hazard Ratios (HR; Cox proportional hazards survival regression analyses) for the incidence of use of ACE inhibitors or ARB during EDIC follow-up computed for 1 SD of the body-weight variability indices expressed as Z-scores. Model 1: adjusted for sex, study treatment allocation during the DCCT, occurrence of pregnancy during the DCCT, and for baseline DCCT characteristics, including age, duration of diabetes, BMI, mean blood pressure, eGFR, circulating levels of HbA1c, total cholesterol and triglycerides, and tobacco smoking. Model 2: similar to Model 1 but with the average values of BMI, mean blood pressure, circulating levels of HbA1c, total cholesterol and triglycerides, and with tobacco smoking during the DCCT+EDIC follow-up replacing the baseline data. See methods for definitions of the indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight and outcomes.

Supplemental Table 4. Risk of outcomes during the DCCT+EDIC follow-up by indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight during the DCCT follow-up, adjusted for growth in height during the DCCT follow-up.

	Model 1		Model 2	
	HR or OR (95% C.I.)	p	HR or OR (95% C.I.)	p
40% eGFR decline				
VIM	1.23 (1.08 – 1.40)	0.002	1.23 (1.07 – 1.39)	0.004
ASV	1.20 (1.05 – 1.35)	0.007	1.17 (1.03 – 1.33)	0.02
SD_bw	1.22 (1.06 – 1.40)	0.005	1.23 (1.06 – 1.42)	0.006
REL_ASV	1.20 (1.05 – 1.35)	0.009	1.18 (1.04 – 1.34)	0.01
Doubling of SCR				
VIM	1.38 (1.14 – 1.65)	0.001	1.35 (1.13 – 1.61)	0.002
ASV	1.28 (1.07 – 1.52)	0.009	1.27 (1.06 – 1.49)	0.009
SD_bw	1.32 (1.08 – 1.60)	0.008	1.34 (1.10 – 1.60)	0.004
REL_ASV	1.29 (1.07 – 1.52)	0.007	1.27 (1.07 – 1.50)	0.009
CKD Stage 3				
VIM	1.40 (1.14 – 1.67)	0.001	1.34 (1.10 – 1.60)	0.004
ASV	1.32 (1.11 – 1.54)	0.002	1.32 (1.11 – 1.56)	0.002
SD_bw	1.33 (1.09– 1.61)	0.007	1.35 (1.09 – 1.63)	0.005
REL_ASV	1.35 (1.12 – 1.60)	0.002	1.33 (1.11 – 1.58)	0.003
Rapid decline in eGFR*				
VIM	1.44 (1.14 – 1.81)	0.003	1.42 (1.08 – 1.88)	0.01
ASV	1.38 (1.12 – 1.70)	0.004	1.31 (1.02 – 1.67)	0.03
SD_bw	1.42 (1.11 – 1.80)	0.006	1.48 (1.10 – 1.98)	0.009
REL_ASV	1.35 (1.07 – 1.68)	0.01	1.35 (1.04 – 1.75)	0.03

A2 albuminuria

VIM	1.19 (1.05 – 1.34)	0.008	1.06 (0.93 – 1.20)	0.38
ASV	1.14 (1.01 – 1.27)	0.03	1.04 (0.92 – 1.16)	0.53
SD_bw	1.13 (0.99– 1.28)	0.08	1.02 (0.89 – 1.17)	0.75
REL_ASV	1.18 (1.06 – 1.32)	0.004	1.07 (0.95 – 1.21)	0.24

A3 albuminuria

VIM	1.36 (1.13 – 1.63)	0.002	1.10 (0.91 – 1.31)	0.32
ASV	1.25 (1.06 – 1.46)	0.008	1.04 (0.88 – 1.20)	0.66
SD_bw	1.25 (1.02 – 1.52)	0.03	1.03 (0.90 – 1.24)	0.74
REL_ASV	1.33 (1.12 – 1.56)	0.001	1.08 (0.91 – 1.27)	0.38

Hazard Ratios (HR; Cox proportional hazards survival regression analyses) for the incidence of outcomes and *Odds Ratios (OR; logistic regression analyses) for the occurrence of Rapid decline in eGFR during follow-up computed for 1 SD of the body-weight variability indices expressed as Z-scores. Model 1: adjusted for sex, study treatment allocation during the DCCT, occurrence of pregnancy during the DCCT, growth in height during the DCCT (delta of height), and for baseline DCCT characteristics, including age, duration of diabetes, BMI, mean blood pressure, eGFR, circulating levels of HbA1c, total cholesterol and triglycerides, and tobacco smoking. Model 2: similar to Model 1 but with the average values of BMI, mean blood pressure, circulating levels of HbA1c, total cholesterol and triglycerides, and with tobacco smoking during the DCCT+EDIC follow-up replacing the baseline data, plus the use of ACE inhibitors or ARB during the EDIC follow-up. See methods for definitions of the indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight and outcomes.

Supplemental Table 5. Risk of outcomes during the DCCT+EDIC follow-up by indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight computed with body-weight measures from baseline to the end of DCCT follow-up

	Model 1		Model 2	
	HR or OR (95% C.I.)	p	HR or OR (95% C.I.)	p
40% eGFR decline				
VIM	1.20 (1.05 – 1.36)	0.009	1.31 (1.11 – 1.53)	0.001
ASV	1.19 (1.04 – 1.34)	0.01	1.19 (1.04 – 1.36)	0.02
SD_bw	1.14 (1.00 – 1.28)	0.04	1.30 (1.09 – 1.54)	0.003
REL_ASV	1.24 (1.09 – 1.41)	0.002	1.24 (1.08 – 1.42)	0.003
Doubling of SCR				
VIM	1.43(1.20 – 1.70)	0.0001	1.34 (1.10 – 1.62)	0.005
ASV	1.38 (1.13 – 1.65)	0.002	1.33 (1.10 – 1.58)	0.004
SD_bw	1.40 (1.10 – 1.73)	0.006	1.31 (1.06 – 1.61)	0.01
REL_ASV	1.50 (1.24 – 1.80)	<0.0001	1.39 (1.16 – 1.64)	0.0006
CKD Stage 3				
VIM	1.28 (1.06 – 1.54)	0.01	1.52 (1.21 – 1.89)	0.0006
ASV	1.31 (1.11 – 1.54)	0.002	1.41 (1.18 – 1.68)	0.0003
SD_bw	1.24 (1.01– 1.50)	0.04	1.48 (1.16 – 1.86)	0.002
REL_ASV	1.40 (1.17 – 1.65)	0.004	1.52 (1.24 – 1.82)	<0.0001
Rapid decline in eGFR*				
VIM	1.57 (1.21 – 2.04)	0.0007	1.51 (1.12 – 2.03)	0.007
ASV	1.51 (1.20 – 1.88)	0.0006	1.38 (1.07 – 1.78)	0.01
SD_bw	1.55 (1.16 – 2.04)	0.003	1.55 (1.13 – 2.13)	0.007
REL_ASV	1.58 (1.24 – 1.99)	0.0001	1.40 (1.07 – 1.81)	0.01

Microalbuminuria

VIM	1.18 (1.02 – 1.36)	0.03	1.00 (0.85 – 1.14)	0.87
ASV	1.15 (1.02 – 1.29)	0.03	1.04 (0.92 – 1.18)	0.50
SD_bw	1.12 (0.96 – 1.30)	0.15	0.98 (0.82 – 1.11)	0.58
REL_ASV	1.20 (1.06 – 1.35)	0.006	1.06 (0.93 – 1.20)	0.40

Macroalbuminuria

VIM	1.35 (1.07 – 1.69)	0.01	1.01 (0.82 – 1.23)	0.91
ASV	1.22 (1.02 – 1.44)	0.03	1.03 (0.87 – 1.21)	0.69
SD_bw	1.22 (0.96 – 1.54)	0.11	0.97 (0.78 – 1.19)	0.76
REL_ASV	1.34 (1.11 – 1.60)	0.003	1.08 (0.90 – 1.28)	0.42

Hazard Ratios (HR; Cox proportional hazards survival regression analyses) for the incidence of outcomes and *Odds Ratios (OR; logistic regression analyses) for the occurrence of Rapid decline in eGFR during follow-up computed for 1 SD of the body-weight variability indices expressed as Z-scores. Model 1: adjusted for sex, study treatment allocation during the DCCT, occurrence of pregnancy during the DCCT, and for baseline DCCT characteristics, including age, duration of diabetes, BMI, mean blood pressure, eGFR, circulating levels of HbA1c, total cholesterol and triglycerides, and tobacco smoking. Model 2: similar to Model 1 but with the average values of BMI, mean blood pressure, circulating levels of HbA1c, total cholesterol and triglycerides, and with tobacco smoking during the DCCT+EDIC follow-up replacing the baseline data, plus the use of ACE inhibitors or ARB during the EDIC follow-up. See methods for definitions of the indices of intraindividual variability of body-weight and outcomes.

Supplemental Figure 1. Flowchart of participants